

EFFECT OF RELATIVE HUMIDITY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CO₂ CURING IN RECOVERED CARBON BLACK NANOMODIFIED MORTARS

Aniya Edwards^{1*}, Rui Bai¹, Raikhan Tokpatayeva¹, Jan Olek¹, Mirian Velay-Lizancos¹

¹Lyles School of Civil and Construction Engineering, Purdue University, West Lafayette, Indiana, USA

*Corresponding Author: Aniya Edwards (edwar242@purdue.edu)

Abstract: Recovered carbon black (RCB) can be an economic alternative to traditional nanomaterials. Recent studies have shown a synergistic effect of CO₂ curing and RCB in increasing the early-age strength of mortars. While the influence of relative humidity (RH) on CO₂ curing has been studied for conventional cementitious materials, its effect on nanomaterial systems remains unexplored. This is especially relevant for RCB, whose hydrophobic nature may influence moisture transport and carbonation behavior. This study investigates the effect of RH on CO₂ curing efficiency in mortars with 0%, 1%, and 2% of RCB (by binder mass). A total of 108 prisms were cast and initially cured under identical conditions. Between 24 to 48 hours after casting, samples were exposed to CO₂ concentrations of 0%, 5%, 10%, and 20% at RH levels of 50%, 70%, and 100%. Carbonation depth (using the phenolphthalein test) and 3-day compressive strength were measured. For mortars without RCB, 70% RH during CO₂ curing yielded the greatest strength improvement. In contrast, RCB-modified mortars showed the highest strength gain at 100% RH. This behavior may be attributed to the hydrophobicity of RCB, which could facilitate CO₂ access to reactive surfaces even under saturated conditions. The extent of carbonation depth is not a good indicator of the effects of CO₂ curing in terms of compressive strength changes, indicating that strength enhancement at high RH is not solely governed by the extent of Ca(OH)₂ carbonation. Results suggest that at high RH, in the presence of RCB, CO₂ curing induces carbonation of other compounds, but QXRD in cement paste would be required for confirmation.

1. Introduction

Durability of concrete elements is a critical factor governing the long-term performance of transportation infrastructure¹. Strength and porosity are two key parameters influencing durability, as they control the resistance to cracking and the ingress of water, chlorides, and other aggressive agents^{2,3}. Traditionally, durability has been improved by reducing the water-to-binder ratio and incorporating highly pozzolanic fine materials, such as silica fume, to refine the pore structure^{4,5}. In recent years, however, novel approaches have been increasingly explored to further improve mechanical performance and reduce porosity.

Among the strategies used to improve the durability of cementitious composites, nanomodification has attracted significant attention due to its ability to refine microstructure, accelerate hydration, and enhance mechanical performance⁶. Various nanomaterials have been investigated for this purpose, including nano-TiO₂^{6,7}, nanosilica (nS)^{8,9}, and cellulose nanofibrils (CNF)¹⁰.

CO₂ curing is another promising approach for reducing porosity and enhancing strength, particularly in precast concrete operations¹¹. Furthermore, a previous study⁶ has shown that combining nano-TiO₂ with CO₂ curing can further refine the pore structure. However, the relatively high cost of nano-TiO₂ limits its broader practical use, prompting the search for more economical alternatives¹². In this context, recovered carbon black (RCB), a recycled carbon-rich material derived from waste tires and batteries, has emerged as a promising substitute.

A recent study¹² explored the potential synergistic effects of CO₂ curing and RCB on the performance of cementitious composites, focusing on early-age compressive strength and CaCO₃ formation. While RCB had minimal impact under standard curing, the incorporation of 2% RCB combined with CO₂ curing significantly increased strength compared to both reference mixtures and CO₂-cured samples without RCB. These results demonstrate the potential of jointly using RCB and CO₂ curing to enhance early strength in precast elements. However, in that study, the curing was conducted at a constant 20% CO₂ concentration and an initial 50% relative humidity (RH), which increased to 90% during carbonation curing due to additional water formation during carbonation. While the effects of RH and CO₂ concentration on curing effectiveness have been investigated for conventional cementitious materials¹³, their influence on nanomodified systems remains unexplored. This question is particularly relevant for RCB-modified mixtures, as the hydrophobic nature of RCB may alter moisture transport and carbonation behavior. Therefore, this study examines the effect of relative humidity on the effectiveness of CO₂ curing for both standard and nanomodified mortars containing RCB.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The main materials used in this study were RCB, Type II cement, tap water, and INDOT No. 23 sand (900 INDOT specs) with a saturated surface-dry relative density of 2.36 and an absorption of 1.54%. While the cement, water, and aggregates used are standard, further definition and characterization of RCB is provided.

Carbon black is a hydrophobic nanomaterial produced from the pyrolysis of hydrocarbons such as petroleum. It consists of primary carbon nanoparticles that agglomerate and are commonly used to impart a black color to materials in tires, automotive components, and electrical products¹⁴. RCB, or recycled carbon black, is obtained by pyrolyzing waste tires; however, this process can introduce impurities from the tires and other commercial manufacturing additives. The RCB used in this study was BolderBlack® from Bolder Industries, with a reported composition of 80–90% carbon and a relative density of 1800 g/cm³.

Loss on ignition (LOI) analysis indicated a carbon content of 83% for this sample. This is evidenced by the reduction in sample volume after LOI testing and the color change from dark black to granulated yellow-beige, as shown in Figures 1(a) and 1(b).

The morphology of the RCB was characterized via Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) using a Tecnai T20 Transmission Electron Microscope and ASTM D3849¹⁵. A sample of RCB was ground with a mortar and pestle, passed through a No. 200 sieve, shear-mixed with superplasticizer, and sonicated to minimize particle agglomeration before observation under the microscope. Selected particle diameters from TEM images were measured and averaged. Evaluation of TEM images shows that primary RCB nanoparticles range from 5-90 nm, while aggregated particles can be as large as 5 μm . The primary particles are irregular in shape, sometimes showing wavy edges, and they agglomerate in irregular patterns, as shown in Figure 1(c).

Figure 1. RCB Pre-LOI (a.), Post LOI (b.), and Under TEM (c.)

2.2 Mix design and curing process

Three mortar mixtures were prepared with RCB concentrations of 0% (RCB0), 1% (RCB1), and 2% (RCB2) by mass of cement at a water-to-binder ratio of 0.42. The aggregate-to-binder ratio was kept constant at 2.1:1 for all mixes. RCB was first added to a portion of the batch water and high-shear mixed for 90 seconds, followed by mixing of a full mortar batch in accordance with ASTM C305¹⁶.

A total of 108 prism samples (40 mm x 40 mm x 160 mm) were cast for this study; with 36 prisms prepared for each mix type. After mixing, the samples underwent a four-phase curing procedure: Fresh Phase, Conditioning Phase, Comparison Phase, and Open-Air Phase (Figure 2(a)). In the Fresh Phase, fresh mortar was molded and covered for 16 ± 1 hours. The samples were then demolded and entered the Conditioning Phase, during which they were stored at 23 ± 1 °C and $50 \pm 5\%$ RH for 8 hours. During the Comparison Phase, 9 samples per mix were designated for normal curing (N) at 23°C and relative humidities of 50%, 70%, or 100%. The remaining 9 samples were subjected to CO₂ curing at 23°C and relative humidities of 50%, 70%, or 100%, and CO₂ concentrations of 5%, 10%, and 20%. After 24 hours under these conditions, all samples were transferred to a curing chamber maintained at of 23 ± 1 °C and an RH of $50 \pm 5\%$ RH until testing at 3 days of age. Figure 2(b) shows the different curing conditions for the Comparison Phase.

Figure 2. (a) Curing Procedures, (b) RH and CO₂ conditions in the Comparison Cure phase.

2.3 Experimental Methods

Early-age strength determination: Since early-age strength development is crucial for precast production, the effects of both RCB and various CO₂ curing methods on early-age strength were assessed. At 3-days of age, samples were split during flexural testing in accordance with ASTM C348¹⁷. Finally, 3-day compressive strength on the prism halves was determined in compliance with ASTM C349¹⁸, to evaluate any correlation between curing conditions, carbonation, and early-age strength.

Phenolphthalein test: Samples were subsequently sprayed with the 1% phenolphthalein solution and allowed to rest for at least 30 minutes after flexural testing. The solution turns pink when it comes into contact with a pH greater than 8.5, while carbonation, which lowers pH, is indicated by no color change. The samples were then evaluated to compare the depth of carbonation by the change in pH¹⁹.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 3 presents the results of the compressive strength tests. Results showed that CO₂ curing is more effective at increasing early strength at higher RH, especially for RCB samples. The mixtures are named as RCBX-Y, where X is RCB content (expressed as a percentage of total binder weight), and Y refers to the curing method (N for non-CO₂ curing, and C for CO₂ curing). For reference samples (RCB0), the greatest improvement occurs at 70% RH; for RCB samples, the greatest improvement in early strength occurs at 100% RH. The hydrophobic nature of RCB provides the mortar with a more hydrophobic surface (Fig. 4), which may help CO₂ reach the surface at high RH.

Figure 3. Compressive Strength results

Figure 4 shows a water droplet from the wettability test at the same time point (0 seconds) for both RC0 and RCB2, cured under the same conditions. These images showed that RCB2 increases hydrophobicity, as expected.

Figure 4. Image of a water droplet - same timeframe

Figure 5 presents the results of the phenolphthalein test. Results show a clear pattern: the higher the RH, the smaller the carbonation depth in the CO₂-cured samples. These carbonation patterns imply that at lower humidities, CO₂ curing reduces pH and CO₂ penetrates deeper into mortar specimens. Thus, the carbonation depth results suggest that the higher the RH, the lower the effect of CO₂ curing in the tested materials.

Figure 5. Carbonation depth images

However, compressive strength results (Figure 3) showed that CO₂ curing is more effective at higher RH, especially for RCB samples. Thus, results showed that the extent of carbonation depth is not a good indicator of the extent of the effects of CO₂ curing in terms of compressive strength, suggesting that the enhancement of compressive strength induced by the CO₂ curing at high RH is not directly linked to the carbonation of Ca(OH)₂, which would have reduced the pH.

4. Conclusions

For non-nanomodified mortar, the 70% RH during CO₂ curing showed the highest effectiveness in enhancing early-age strength. In contrast, for samples containing RCB, 100% RH during CO₂ curing resulted in the greatest improvement in strength. The hydrophobic nature of RCB, which makes the mortar surface more hydrophobic, may help CO₂ reach the surface even at high RH.

Furthermore, results showed that the extent of carbonation depth is not a good indicator of the extent of the effects of CO₂ curing in terms of compressive strength, suggesting that the enhancement of compressive strength induced by the CO₂ curing at high RH is not directly linked to the carbonation of Ca(OH)₂, which would have lead to an increased carbonation depth, that was not observed on the phenolphthalein results.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the financial support provided for this study by the Transportation Infrastructure Precast Innovation Center (TRANS-IPIC) through the University Transportation Center program of the US Department of Transportation, Office of the Assistant Secretary for Research and Technology (OST-R) under Grant No. 69A3552348333.

References

1. Alexander, M. & Beushausen, H. Durability, service life prediction, and modelling for reinforced concrete structures – review and critique. *Cement and Concrete Research* vol. 122 17–29 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2019.04.018> (2019).
2. Chen, H. J., Huang, S. S., Tang, C. W., Malek, M. A. & Ean, L. W. Effect of curing environments on strength, porosity and chloride ingress resistance of blast furnace slag cement concretes: A construction site study. *Constr. Build. Mater.* **35**, 1063–1070 (2012).
3. Rodriguez, F. B. *et al.* Evaluation of Durability of 3D-Printed Cementitious Materials for Potential Applications in Structures Exposed to Marine Environments. in *RILEM Bookseries* vol. 37 175–181 (Springer Science and Business Media B.V., 2022).
4. Basheer, L., Kropp, J. & Cleland, D. J. *Assessment of the Durability of Concrete from Its Permeation Properties: A Review.* *Construction and Building Materials* vol. 15 (2001).
5. Alexander, M. G. & Magee, B. J. *Durability Performance of Concrete Containing Condensed Silica Fume.* *Cement and Concrete Research* vol. 29 (1999).
6. Moro, C., Francioso, V. & Velay-Lizancos, M. Modification of CO₂ capture and pore structure of hardened cement paste made with nano-TiO₂ addition: Influence of water-to-cement ratio and CO₂ exposure age. *Constr. Build. Mater.* **275**, (2021).
7. Chen, J., Kou, S. C. & Poon, C. S. Hydration and properties of nano-TiO₂ blended cement composites. *Cem. Concr. Compos.* **34**, 642–649 (2012).
8. Hou, P. *et al.* Modification effects of colloidal nanoSiO₂ on cement hydration and its gel property. *Compos. B Eng.* **45**, 440–448 (2013).
9. Huang, D., Velay-Lizancos, M. & Olek, J. A Comparative Study of the Impact of Nano-TiO₂ and Nano-silica on the Durability of Concretes Cured at Different Temperatures. in *Procedia Structural Integrity* vol. 67 61–79 (Elsevier B.V., 2025).
10. Wang, Y. *et al.* Cellulose nanofibers and limestone filler enable high-performance, sustainable, and cost-efficient printable concrete. *Nat. Commun.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-026-69373-5> (2026) doi:10.1038/s41467-026-69373-5.
11. Ravikumar, D. *et al.* Carbon dioxide utilization in concrete curing or mixing might not produce a net climate benefit. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, (2021).
12. Edwards, A., Tokpatayeva, R., Olek, J. & Velay-Lizancos, M. Synergistic Effects of CO₂ Curing and Recovered Carbon Black Nano additives on Early Age Performance of Cementitious Composites. *Proceedings of the C3 Symposium 2025* <https://doi.org/10.5703/1288284317996> (2025).
13. Xu, Z. *et al.* Effects of temperature, humidity and CO₂ concentration on carbonation of cement-based materials: A review. *Construction and Building Materials* vol. 346 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.128399> (2022).
14. Sansotera, M. *et al.* Highly hydrophobic carbon black obtained by covalent linkage of perfluorocarbon and perfluoropolyether chains on the carbon surface. *Chemistry of Materials* **21**, 4498–4504 (2009).
15. Test Method for Carbon Black--Morphological Characterization of Carbon Black Using Electron Microscopy. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1520/D3849-22> (2022).
16. Practice for Mechanical Mixing of Hydraulic Cement Pastes and Mortars of Plastic Consistency. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1520/C0305-20> (2020).
17. Test Method for Flexural Strength of Hydraulic-Cement Mortars. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1520/C0348-21> (2021).

18. Test Method for Compressive Strength of Hydraulic-Cement Mortars (Using Portions of Prisms Broken in Flexure). Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1520/C0349-24> (2024).
19. Lopez-Arias, M., Castillo, A., Bai, R. & Velay-Lizancos, M. Effect of TiO₂-based surface treatment on the CO₂ reduction in concrete pavements. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **215**, (2025).